

STUDY ON HYBRID INJECTION MOULDING OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC

Masao Tomioka*¹, Takeshi Ishikawa¹ and Tatsuya Tanaka²

¹Toyohashi Research Laboratories, MITSUBISHI RAYON CO., LTD.
1-2, Ushikawa-dohri 4-Chome, Toyohashi-shi, Aichi 440-8601, Japan

*Email: tomioka_ma@mrc.co.jp, web page: <http://www.mrc.co.jp/>

²Faculty of Engineering and Science, Doshisha University
Tatara Miyakodani 1-3, Kyotanabe, Kyoto 610-0321, Japan

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ABSTRACT

We employed the CFRTP (carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic) sheet as the reinforcement and SFP (short fibre pellet) as over-moulded polymer. The SFP was injected over the CFRTP sheet which was pre-heated before clamping the mould. The mechanical property of the hybrid moulded product depends not only on the design of reinforcement and over-moulded polymer but on the interfacial condition between them. Therefore, we achieved the high mechanical property controlling the interfacial temperature designing the injection temperature and the pre-heat process precisely.

The hybrid injection moulding system can catch up with the high-cycle automobile assembly line due to its excellent productivity. Therefore the suitable design of CFRTP's, the interface controlling the process conditions can produce the high cost performance vehicular components.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, reducing the CO₂ emission from the vehicles is an urgent issue to solve concerning the global warming. Many kinds of studies have been carried out from the view points of light weight materials, energy resources, and so on. The carbon fibre reinforced composites are focused because of their light weight and high mechanical properties. Among them, the carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) is considered as a material for automotive parts due to its short moulding time. However the cost of carbon fibre keeps high level, so the improvement of the cost performance is necessary. In order to overcome the cost barrier, the multi-material idea is proposed [1]. The high cost material such as carbon fibre is used only at the right place where high mechanical strength is required. According to the idea, the hybrid injection moulding system which includes preforming of inserted material in the mould before over-moulding in single unit of injection machine has been developed [2]. Fig. 1 shows hybrid moulding process. Pre-heated thermoplastic inserted material is placed in the mould and preformed by clamping the mould. Then ribs or others are moulded by injection over the inserted material. The system shows advantages of short cycle time, good cost performance, and flexibility of geometry. Although properties of mouldings produced by this system is affected by moulding conditions, it is not fully investigated. In particular, there is room for study on the effects of process conditions on the interface between the injected and inserted materials.

Therefore, this study shows the influences of the temperature of inserted and injected materials on the adhesion of the insert-injection interface.

Figure 1: Hybrid injection moulding process

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

Carbon fibre (PYROFIL® CF tow TR 50S15L, tensile strength 4900MPa, tensile modulus 240GPa, supplied by MITSUBISHI RAYON CO., LTD.) was used as reinforcing fibre and maleic-anhydride-grafted polypropylene (m-PP, supplied by MITSUBISHI CHEMICAL CORP.) was used as matrix polymer of UD prepreg. Short carbon fibre reinforced polypropylene pellet (PYROFIL® pellet PP-C-30A, supplied by MITSUBISHI RAYON CO., LTD.) of which carbon fibre content was 30wt% (fibre volume fraction of 18%) was used as the injection material.

2.2 Preparation of UD prepreg

The carbon fibre tows were spread to an areal weight of 78g/m^2 and laminated from both sides by the cast m-PP films of $40\mu\text{m}$ thickness. This laminated sheet was heated to 260°C and passed through a roll gap under a specific pressure to impregnate fibre with m-PP. The resulting sample was UD prepreg used for the insert material of hybrid injection moulding. Fibre volume fraction and thickness of the UD prepreg was 35% and 0.12mm , respectively.

2.3 Preparation of hybrid moulding

Hybrid injection moulding machine used in this study was incorporated horizontal injection moulding machine (80-ton clamping force model, manufactured by TOYO MACHINERY & METAL CO., LTD.) with vertical mould clamping system and IR heater, as shown in Fig. 2. An end-gated mould was used to produce the ribbed-hat-channel samples shown in Fig. 3. The length, top width, height and thickness of the samples were 198 mm, 22 mm, 18mm and 1.5 mm, respectively. Hybrid moulded samples were prepared in the method as shown in Fig. 1. One ply of the UD prepreg sheet cut to $190\text{mm} [0^\circ] \times 55\text{mm} [90^\circ]$ was placed on the lower mould and was pre-headed by IR heater. The heated UD prepreg sheet was preformed by clamping the mould. Then the short carbon fibre reinforced polypropylene was injected into the mould. Table 1 shows the process conditions of the hybrid mouldings. The specimens with various pre-heating times and with various cylinder temperatures were prepared in this study. Cooling time was increased to demould the specimens in the cases of high the cylinder temperature.

Figure 2: Schematic view of the hybrid injection moulding machine

Figure 3: Shape of hybrid moulding

	specimen					
	a	b	c	d	e	f
Pre-heating time (sec)	5	10	15	20	5	5
Mould Temperature (°C)	40	40	40	40	40	40
Screw rotation speed (r/min)	100	100	100	100	100	100
Injection pressure (MPa)	80	80	80	80	80	80
Back pressure (MPa)	1	1	1	1	1	1
Holding pressure (MPa)	40	40	40	40	40	40
Cylinder Temperature (°C)	200	200	200	200	230	260
Holding time (sec)	3	3	3	3	3	3
Cooling time (sec)	10	10	10	10	20	30

Table 1: Conditions of preparation specimens

2.4 Temperature measurement in pre-heating

Surface temperature of the UD prepreg sheet during pre-heating was measured by type K thermocouple (Chromel-Alumel) to investigate the efficiency of the pre-heating. Measurement point was the interface between the prepreg and the injection material where the opposite of the directly heated side by the IR heater as shown in Fig. 4. Conducted heating times were changed from 5 to 20 seconds. The temperature profiles were recorded from the start of the pre-heating to the cooling process after the stop of heating. In this measurement, the over-moulding was not completed in order to prevent the thermocouples from claming by the mould.

Figure 4: Schematic view of temperature measurement position

2.5 Evaluation of interfacial adhesion

Evaluation of interfacial adhesion was carried out by conducting 3-point bending test of specimens with following conditions; testing machine was Instron® 5565, distance of supports was 120 mm, cross-head speed of testing machine was 5mm/min, radii of loading nose and supports shape were 5 mm and 2mm, respectively. The specimens were set the hat-top downside as shown in Fig. 5. Fig. 6

shows a 3-point bending load-displacement curve of specimen (a). In this bending test, interfacial delamination between the prepreg and injection material was observed at the first of stress yield point (load 1287N, displacement 2.6mm) of the load-displacement curve. Fig. 7 shows specimens before and after the interfacial debonding. In this study, the load of first yield point was recorded as an index of interfacial adhesion in all of specimens.

Figure 5: View of 3-point bending test of hybrid moulding

Figure 6: Load-displacement curve of hybrid moulding (specimen a)

(a) Before the bending test

(b) After the delamination

Figure 7: Specimens before and after the interfacial delamination

3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Temperature measurement

Fig. 8 shows temperature profiles of prepreg's surface in pre-heating by the IR heater. With the increase of heating time, the temperature of prepreg surface increased. The highest temperature of

surface at the heating time of 5 seconds, 10 seconds, 15 seconds and 20 seconds were 151 ° C, 228 ° C, 272 ° C and 298 ° C, respectively.

In addition, there were shoulders at 135 ° C of rising curves and at 100 ° C of descending curves. The shoulder points show the changes between the melted and the crystalline state of thermoplastic of the prepreg sheet. It is found that the preforming is possible because the thermoplastic is melted within 5 second heating.

Figure 8: Temperature profiles of prepreg interface

3.2 Interfacial adhesion

In all of the 3-point bending tests of specimens (a) - (f), the interfacial debondings were occurred at the first load-yield-point. These load values are shown in Fig. 9 and 10. Fig. 9 shows the effect of pre-heating time by the IR heater. Although the improvement of interfacial delamination load was observed with an increase of pre-heating time up to 15 seconds, the load of 20 seconds heating was lower than 15 seconds. It was suggested that the presence of low-molecular-weight components which were generated by thermal degradation reduced the adhesion.

Fig. 10 shows the effect of the cylinder temperature. The interfacial delamination load was linearly improved with the increase of the cylinder temperature. Moreover, the increase of the cylinder temperature was more effective than surface temperature of the prepreg because the heat capacity of the prepreg was much smaller than that of the injection material.

Figure 9: Effect of pre-heating time

Figure 10: Effect of Cylinder temperature

4 CONCLUSION

Based on these experimental results, some conclusions can be derived as follows:

- The cylinder temperature of the injection machine and the surface temperature of inserted material affect the interfacial adhesion in the hybrid moulding.
- The interfacial temperature is important factor when the interface was builded in the over-moulding process. High adhesion load can be achieved by the high interfacial temperature without the thermal decomposition of polymers.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Plath, Lightweight Design Materials and sustainability for Automotive Applications, Proceedings of the 1st International Conference & Exhibition on Thermoplastic Composites 2012, Bremen, Germany, October 29-30, Congress Center Bremen, pp. 11.
- [2] TOYO MACHINERY & METAL CO., LTD., “CFRTP Hybrid Molding System”, *IPF Japan 2014, Chiba, Japan, October 28-November 1, 2014*, Makuhari Messe, booth 62504.